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Performance of pilot-scale plant: An integrated settler based anaerobic biofilm reactor for the treatment of domestic wastewater

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Abstract

In a developing country like India where 68.84% people live in villages with insufficient sanitation and a poor infrastructure for waterborne sanitation. Government institutions, private water agencies and research institutes are engaged in exploring all alternative domestic wastewater treatment options at the onsite level. Integrated settler based anaerobic biofilm reactor (ISBABR) is a research initiative in the field of domestic wastewater treatment that this paper reflects the study of its performance on a pilot scale. The ISBABR is designed on the basic concept of conventional septic tanks and anaerobic biofilm reactors. The main motive of this research project to develop an electric free, minimum capital cost, low operation and maintenance based onsite treatment system. In this paper we discussed on only treatment of grey water generated from hostel with the help of ISBABR. The ISBABR was constructed based on the design of a laboratory scale reactor (57 liters), which treated the actual sewage at 24 hours HRT. The reactor was started without inoculation of any biomass. Results of reactor in terms TSS, BOD and COD was 81%, 83%, and 81% removal efficiency respectively. In bacterial analysis, the removal efficiency of the system was found to be higher than 84 percent, which indicates good performance of the ISBABR system at pilot scale.

Keywords

Anaerobic treatment, onsite sanitation system, domestic wastewater, grey water, hydraulic retention time

1. INTRODUCTION

The majority percentage of world population living without proper sanitation[1] facilities resides in India (UNICEF and WHO, 2019)[2]. “Swachh Bharat Abhiyan” the nationwide cleanliness and sanitation campaign launched by the Government of India,[3] which is estimated to cost \$ 1.5 billion,[4] has the capacity to treat only 37.6% of the total sewage generated[5]. India like many other developing countries around the world depends upon traditional ways to dispose domestic sewage, the most common of which are septic tanks and pit latrines[6]. The persisting problem with these technologies is seepage through their walls which leads to contamination of nearby soils and sometimes even groundwater. All these factors add up to economic losses in the form of additional healthcare costs, loss of productive time and

mortality in the absence of adequate sanitation. Wastewater treatment through onsite sanitation is a significant challenge in developing countries. In India 68.84% of its population lives in villages where no good wastewater treatment facility is available[7] and what is available has become outdated. At the household level, maximum wastewater is directly disposed of in open water bodies which further deteriorates the quality of water sources. In the last five years, Indian government constructed approximately ten crores “twin pit toilets” through “Swachh Bharata Abhiyaan”[8] but they are only capable in storing the sewage and not treating them. It will require money and treatment plant for further treatment, which will affect the economy, sanitation and health issues, so the onsite sanitation system can be the best alternative [9]. Today, many treatment systems at centralized level in India are doing well, but when it comes to onsite treatment of sewage or wastewater, despite the method being innovative, due to high capital, operation & maintenance costs, adoption of these technologies by the people have become difficult. To avoid this CST is used as an alternative, but its low removal efficiency is a major concern [10] which cannot be overlooked and requires an early solution. Our ISBABR is designed as an onsite sanitation system meaning it treats the sewage at the point of its generation and then reuse/disposes it. The system will be tested first with greywater, then mixed (grey and black water) and lastly with black water to check its performance, accessibility and economic viability in solving the non-sewer sanitation problem. In this paper however we will be discussing the treatment capabilities of the system to treat greywater. Greywater is normally a waste of bathroom shower, washbasin, bathtub, kitchen waste, sink and laundry wastewater etc [11]. There is little to no faecal contamination. It is also known as sullage. Black water is toilet flush [12] wastewater having solid contents, BOD, COD and faecal coliform range much higher than greywater.

The schematic diagram of the system is shown in fig.1. The system is divided into three parts. The first chamber works as a settling chamber while the second and third chambers act as anaerobic biofilm filters. All three chambers are connected to each other according to the up-flow direction of water movement. Fill Pac media was filled in the second chamber and the third chamber was filled with MBBR media. Both media are used as biofilm filers [13]. This study provides a short overview of ISBABR performance and its applications for reuse purposes.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Configuration of the ISBABR system

Figure 1. shows the schematic diagram of pilot-scale treatment unit with description. The ISBABR present inside the pilot plant has a working capacity of 5670 litres and the entire treatment unit is constructed with the help of regular building materials. This ISBABR system consists of three rectangular chambers whose unit dimensions are 1.22m x 1.22m x 1.95m (LxBxH), 1.22m x 0.61m x 1.90m (LxBxH) and 1.22m x 0.61m x 1.82m (LxBxH) respectively. The flow of wastewater in the compartments of ISBABR system is in the upward direction from the beginning till end. The compartments are connected through vertical PVC pipe (110 mm diameter) as clearly shown in fig.1. The 2nd and 3rd compartments of ISBABR system was filled with Fill Pac media and MBBR media. The manufacturing details of media are mentioned in Table.1.

Table.1 Description of plastic media

Description	Fill-Pac Media	MBBR Media
Type of Media	Wheel (Flower) Media	Cylindrical
Structure	Cylindrical shape with internal ribs	Trapezoidal Cylindrical
Media size	152mm*51mm	16*22
Raw Material	Poly propylene	Poly propylene
Specific Gravity	0.9 gm/cm ³	0.90-0.95 gm/cm ³
Surface Area	100 m ² /m ³	350 m ² /m ³
Colour	Black	Black
Max. operating Temperature	80°C	80°C

2.2 Feed flow pattern

The ISBABR was run under daily water demand to maintain 24-36hour hydraulic retention time and the flow was not managed through the pump. The design and construction of the reactor has been done by maintaining the water head so that there is no obstruction in the flow, and it can easily reach from the inlet to the outlet with the help of gravitational force. The pilot scale condition does not have a flow rate constant; it works on non-steady flow condition which arises due to shock loading. From 6:00 to 9:00 water demand is higher as compared to from 9 to 12 during which it reduces. From 12:00 to 2:00 water demand graph goes up again a little bit because of lunch hour in the student hostel. It falls again after the lunch hour but rises in the evening from 6:00 to 9:00. After that water demand falls in the night. The hydraulic retention time increases as the number of students decreases and vice-versa.

2.3 System set-up, seeding and start-up

This pilot plant is constructed inside the Vinayak Boys Hostel complex near Manipal University, Jaipur, Dahmi Kalan. The hostel accommodates 36 children. The total volume of pilot plant is 6441 litres and its working volume is approximately 5670 litres. The system first started treating only greywater therefore seeding was not required.

2.4 Experimental Methodology

During the duration of this study, which was around four months, samples were collected single time in a week from the inlet and outlet point of the system and was tested at the Environmental Engineering Lab of Manipal University, Jaipur. To verify the authenticity of results, samples were also tested at Jagdamba Laboratory which is NABL accredited. The collected samples were analysed for pH, temperature, TSS, BOD, COD, orthophosphate and NH₄-N parameters.

Fig.1: The schematic diagram of pilot-scale unit: ISBABR

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The sample is collected from the inlet (influent sampling) and outlet (effluent sampling) point by sampler and filled in a 1 liter wide mouth plastic bottle for testing in the Environmental Engineering Lab of the Civil Engineering Department, Manipal University, Jaipur, where its physical chemical and biological parameters are analysed. In this study, the results were analysed on weekly basis which are shown in Fig-2 through a complete graphical representation of wastewater parameters (Total suspended solid-TSS, Biochemical oxygen demand-BOD, Chemical oxygen demand-COD, Ortho Phosphate-OP and Ammonical nitrogen-NH₄-N).

Table. 2 presents the average data of inlet, outlet concentration and removal efficiency of the pilot scale treatment system. The pH of samples obtained from both the inlet and outlet sections are slightly alkaline, and their average temperature is around 30±4 degrees which is a very favourable temperature for anaerobic systems. The average TSS concentration in inlet is 209±55 after treatment it removes 81±6% suspended solid from raw greywater. Similarly, average removal efficiency of BOD, COD, Ortho Phosphate and Ammonical-N concentrations are 81±6, 81±8, 28.7±12.5 and 23.4±10.37 respectively.

Fig.2. Evaluation of the parameter concentration of inlet and outlet with %removal efficiency (a) TSS, (b) COD, (c) BOD, (d) Ortho Phosphate and (e) Ammonical Nitrogen.

Table-2 Avg. data and performance of pilot scale ISBABR

S No.	Wastewater Parameter	Inlet	Outlet	% Avg. Removal Efficiency
1.	pH	7.5±0.6	7.5±0.6	-
2.	Temp (°C)	30±4	30±4	-
3.	TSS(mg/l)	209±55	38±15	81±6
4.	BOD(mg/l)	144±42	23±15	83±5
5.	COD(mg/l)	286.15±90	52±22	81±8
6.	Ortho Phosphate(mg/l)	2.1±1.84	1.4±1.70	28.7±12.5
7.	Ammonical-N(mg/l)	7.3±3.5	5.6±3.10	23.4±10.37
8.	Bacterial No.(MPN/100ml)	>1200	80±45	

*Average value± standard deviation

4. CONCLUSION

Designed ISBABR is a very effective treatment system at pilot scale for the treatment of grey water as evident from its analytical results with very little operation and maintenance costs, which shows its affordability and feasibility. Based on the performances of the onsite sanitation system (currently used in India) and the present ISBABR system it was found that the latter had a much higher percentage of removal efficiency. According to the results, removal efficiency of this system in term of TSS, BOD, COD, orthophosphate and ammonical nitrogen was 81%, 83%, 81%, 28% and 23%, respectively. After this the system will be tested for its performance efficiency with mix water (black water and grey water) and only black water, which will be mentioned in the next research papers.

Therefore, the present pilot scale study is a feasible option of onsite domestic wastewater treatment for the people living in the unsewered rural and semi urban areas of the developing countries like India.

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